

Realtime FHD Low-Latency Video Communication with BCM2835

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Abstract: This paper describes a real-time Full-HD (1080p) low-latency video communication system using the Raspberry Pi Zero W (BCM2835, VideoCore IV) within a local 5G environment. The system targets on-board camera applications requiring low power, compact design, and lossless transmission. Using the H.264 hardware encoder, the BCM2835 achieves 30 FPS streaming with an end-to-end latency of about 80 ms, while consuming only 0.25 A and maintaining nearly zero CPU load. Traffic analysis shows that, due to its single-core DDR2 configuration, packet transmission is spiky, unlike the smoother traffic of dedicated encoder devices. These results demonstrate that the BCM2835 can provide energy-efficient real-time FHD streaming, though traffic shaping will be necessary for stable multi-stream operation in local 5G systems.

Fig. 1: bcm2835 Overview

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1. Introduction

Modern embedded video systems are increasingly required to

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achieve low power consumption, compact form factor, high resolution, low latency, and lossless (noise-free) transmission simultaneously—despite the conflicting nature of these performance goals.

This paper introduces the software design and implementation of a real-time Full-HD (1080p) video transmission system built on the Raspberry Pi Zero W, which integrates the BCM2835 SoC and VideoCore IV GPU. The proposed architecture demonstrates that even with limited hardware resources, it is possible to realize energy-efficient, space-saving, and low-latency video streaming suitable for edge or mobile embedded applications within a local 5G environment.

2. Client-Side Latency

The **BCM2835 SoC** used in the Raspberry Pi Zero W provides an H.264 hardware accelerator via its VideoCore IV GPU. When rotation operations are disabled, the system can continuously execute the processing stages (1..6 in Figure 1) at Full HD (1080p) resolution and maintain a steady 30 frames per second throughput.

However, when a 180-degree rotation is applied, the effective number of scan lines increases to 1920, and the H.264 encoding process becomes the initial bottleneck, introducing cumulative video latency. This indicates that real-time encoding performance is highly sensitive to the pixel traversal pattern and memory layout used by the GPU’s encoder pipeline.

According to the Raspberry Pi userland issue reports ^{*1}, the typical latency for a 1280 × 720 (720p) 30 FPS configuration is approximately within the same range observed in our measurements.

Table 1: BCM2835 Latency

Function	Latency	Note
Sensor (photon → GPU)	≈33 ms	Sensor exposure and data transfer to GPU
Rolling-shutter delay	≈20 ms	Depends on sensor readout timing
ISP processing (stabilization OFF)	≈10 ms	Includes color correction and tone mapping
H.264 encoding	≈20 ms	Dependent on frame size / number of scan lines
UDP segmentation & transmission	≈200 μs	Negligible compared with upstream stages

2.1 Encoding Bottleneck

The processing pipeline from the image sensor and shutter control through the Image Signal Processor (ISP) operates in a pipelined and parallelized manner. However, the encoding stage begins only after ISP processing is fully completed, and therefore functions as a sequential stage within the overall workflow. As a result, H.264 encoding performance directly determines the upper limit of the system’s end-to-end throughput and becomes the primary bottleneck in achieving real-time video transmission.

imx219/ Raspberry Pi CameraV2/1280x720 30 fps						
sensor						CSI-2
GPU line						
ISP processing						
Encoding						GPU
time	0	33	20	10	20	

Fig. 2: Pipeline timing

3. Power Consumption

When focusing on power efficiency, the system exhibited an almost zero CPU utilization during video streaming. Power consumption remained stable at approximately 0.25 A, indicating that the SoC and GPU handled the video processing workload highly efficiently without significant CPU involvement. This result confirms that the BCM2835 (VideoCore IV) architecture is well suited for continuous low-power operation in real-time video transmission scenarios.

Fig. 3: Power Consumption

4. Traffic Analysis

The BCM2835 operates in a single-core environment with DDR2 memory, which imposes strict bandwidth and concurrency limitations. An attempt was made to copy encoded I and P frames into a temporary buffer to smooth network traffic; however, this approach caused performance degradation, preventing the system from maintaining a 30 FPS frame rate. To avoid latency spikes and throughput collapse, the encoded frames are instead directly enqueued into the UDP protocol stack within the callback context, eliminating unnecessary memory copy overhead and preserving real-time streaming stability.

system	Cma 64MB					
	VideoCore 512MB (gpu_mem)	codec camera legacy frame-buffer firmware GLES drive(Pi0-3)				

Fig. 4: System Memory Strategy

*1 <https://github.com/raspberrypi/userland/issues/243>

4.1 Traffic Characteristics under Resource Constraints

Due to the limited computational and memory resources of the BCM2835 platform, it is difficult to perform traffic smoothing on the client side. As a result, the packet transmission pattern exhibits a highly peaked distribution, as illustrated in Figure 5, when observed over 10 ms intervals.

In the target deployment scenario, up to six on-board camera streams are transmitted simultaneously. When the transmission spikes from multiple devices coincide, congestion can occur across multiple layers of the system—including network buffers, protocol queues, and even wireless channel time-slices in the local 5G environment.

These observations indicate that additional traffic-shaping mechanisms or temporal offset scheduling would be required to maintain stable throughput under multi-stream operation.

Fig. 5: Mobile type Traffic analyze(BCM2835)

Fig. 6: Traffic distribution (10 ms intervals) comparison between BCM2835 callback transmission and dedicated H.264 encoder device. The dedicated encoder achieves a smoother traffic pattern.

6. Conclusion

This study evaluated a real-time Full-HD low-latency video transmission system implemented on the BCM2835 (VideoCore IV) platform under a local 5G network environment. While the system achieved stable 30 FPS streaming and demonstrated excellent power efficiency with minimal CPU utilization, its traffic characteristics—highly spiky due to single-core and DDR2 constraints—caused significant performance degradation when transmitted through the local 5G channel.

The results indicate that the burstiness of UDP packet transmission is amplified by the 5G network scheduling mechanism, leading to frame drops, increased jitter, and a notable decline in perceived video quality. In conclusion, although the BCM2835 platform is capable of efficient real-time encoding and low-power operation, traffic shaping and rate-control mechanisms are essential to maintain consistent image quality when operating over local 5G infrastructure.

Table 2: Video Transmission Parameters

Parameter	Value	Note
Resolution	1080p	1920×1080 pixels
Frame rate	30 FPS	
Network traffic	8–10 Mbps	Average bitrate during streaming
Keyframe interval	90	One keyframe every 3 s

5. Comparison with Dedicated Encoder Equipment

For reference, packet traffic was also measured from a stationary H.264 hardware encoder with similar video characteristics. When aggregated in 10 ms intervals, the transmission traffic from this dedicated device showed a significantly smoother and more uniform distribution, as illustrated in Figure 6. Unlike the BCM2835 implementation, where packets are transmitted directly from the callback function and exhibit spiky behavior, the dedicated encoder system performs effective traffic smoothing, resulting in a stable and evenly distributed transmission pattern.

Fig. 7: Traffic Pattern(L5G)